

The alkali soil in Awagarh, Uttar Pradesh, had a loamy texture with initial pH 9.2, EC 1.4 dS/m, 38% exchangeable Na, hydraulic conductivity 0.019 cm/h, and 2.0% CaCO₃ for the surface 0-15 cm soil. Pyrites containing 22% S (4 t/ha) was applied at field moisture capacity. It was broadcast, mixed in the top 10-12 cm soil, and good quality tubewell water ponded for 1 wk to leach down soluble salts. Seedlings of 35-d-old Jaya rice were transplanted. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. Increasing pyrites fineness to 3 mm and allowing 1 wk before mixing pyrites into the soil increased yields significantly (see table). Applying 5-mm pyrites 1 wk before mixing into alkali soils was most efficient for reclamation. □

Effect of fineness and time of application of pyrites on rice yield and reclamation of alkali soil of Awagarh, Uttar Pradesh.

	Yield		Soil (0-15 cm) characteristics after rice				
	Grain (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)	pH ₂	EC ₂ (dS/m)	ESP	HC (cm/h)	CaCO ₃ (%)
Pyrites fineness (mm)							
<3	3.58	6.40	8.40	.61	21	.067	0.68
3-5	3.34	5.28	8.57	.65	25	.064	1.01
5-10	2.71	5.00	8.86	.90	30	.034	1.50
Time (wk before mixing into soil)							
0	2.84	4.85	8.76	.83	29	.042	1.18
1	3.45	6.24	8.53	.71	24	.062	1.00
2	3.34	5.84	8.50	.64	23	.067	1.00
CD (0.05) for fineness or application time	0.42	0.88	0.09	0.10	3	.08	0.22

Response of rice to input factors in farmers' fields

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Rice response to three input factors — variety, plant population, and fertilizer — was studied in farmers' fields during 1985 kharif (wet season) at five locations using a randomized complete block design with three replications. The varieties tested were IR6 (local) and

Yield gap and percentage contribution of individual input factors. D.I. Khan, Pakistan, 1985 kharif.

Yield response of rice to input factors in farmers' fields. Pakistan 1985 kharif.^a

Level ^b of input factors			Yield (t/ha)
Variety	Plant population	Fertilizer	
F	F	F	3.4
R	F	F	4.4
F	R	F	4.3
R	R	F	5.4
F	F	R	4.4
R	F	R	4.6
F	R	R	5.0
R	R	R	6.5
LSD (.05)			1.4
(.01)			1.9

^aAV of 5 locations, 3 replications. ^bF = farmers' practice, R = recommended practice.

KS282 (improved). Plant populations were 125,000 and 250,000 hills/ha, and fertilizer rates were 75-22 and 120-40 kg NP/ha. All P and 50% N were applied before transplanting, and the remaining N was topdressed 30 d after transplanting. All other recommended cultural practices were followed.

The highest yield (6.5 t/ha) was produced by all recommended inputs,

followed by recommended variety and plant population (see table). The yield gap — 3.1 t/ha — was significant (see figure). Low plant population was the main constraint to high rice yield. □

N fertilizer (urea) topdressed on unsaturated soil and deep-placed using reflooding water

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We evaluated a simple, practical, and efficient technique for deep placement of urea topdressed in irrigated ricefields. The technique combined N fertilizer application with soil moisture control.

Urea was topdressed on drained ricefields and the fields reflooded immediately. The fertilizer was deep-placed in the reduced zone by the infiltrating water.

The experiment was laid out in a clay loam soil, pH 6.2, 3.28% organic matter, 0.22% total N, 0.06% total P, and 2.01% total K. Fertilizer N efficiency was substantially increased compared with conventional broadcasting of N fertilizer on flooded ricefields (see table). □